

Results of a survey on research data management in low-temperature plasma science

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Are you generally of the opinion that a standardized storage and documentation of modeling and simulation procedures in accordance with suitable data models and metadata standards could help to ensure the quality and re-usability of data obtained from such methods? Please comment on your opinion. 37

Preface

The necessity and potential of systematic archiving and publication of digital research data in the sense of open science are increasingly seen in the scientific community. In this context, the **F**indability, **A**ccessibility, **I**nteroperability, **R**e-usability, and quality assurance of research data in accordance with the **FAIR** Data Principles¹ are essential factors for the efficient interdisciplinary re-use of data and the elimination of reservations against data publication and re-use for data-driven science.

This document summarises the results of an online community survey, which was conducted from 2nd June 2020 to 31st July 2020 within the framework of the project “Quality Assurance and Linking of Research Data in Plasma Technology - QPTDat” (funded 2019–2022 by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) in Germany, project numbers 16QK03A, 16QK03B and 16QK03C). The survey aimed at the evaluation of the status quo regarding research data management in the field of low-temperature plasma science as well as the identification of experimental and computational methods with great relevance to be used as a first reference for the design and testing of quality criteria and (meta)data models for research data management.

Survey tool

The online survey was conducted using a self-hosted LimeSurvey instance at <http://survey.plasma-mds.org/index.php/352444> (not active anymore). The original survey code is available in xml format along with this document on Zenodo². In total, 71 persons took part in the survey and 38 complete answers were obtained.

Results

This section lists and visualises the results of the survey³. The results have been incorporated into developments in the QPTDat project and will be discussed in future publications.

In which country is the institution you work at?

Answer	Count	Percentage
Germany	26	36,62%
Netherlands	5	7,04%
China	3	4,23%
Spain	3	4,23%
France	2	2,82%
Italy	2	2,82%
United Kingdom	2	2,82%
United States of America	2	2,82%
Armenia	1	1,41%
Brazil	1	1,41%
Canada	1	1,41%
Czech Republic	1	1,41%
Hungary	1	1,41%
India	1	1,41%
Japan	1	1,41%

¹ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7841215>

³ In free text comments from participants, spelling errors were coherently corrected.

Mexico	1	1,41%
Romania	1	1,41%
Slovenia	1	1,41%
Switzerland	1	1,41%
No answer	5	7,04%
Not completed or Not displayed	10	14,08%

What is your position?

Answer	Count	Percentage
PhD student	11	15,49%
Postdoc	11	15,49%
Researcher	27	38,03%
Technician / Engineer	0	0,00%
Other	4	5,63%
No answer	8	11,27%
Not completed or Not displayed	10	14,08%

Comments (other):

- Assistant Professor
- Professor
- Professor
- Intern

Which methods are you most familiar with?

Answer	Count	Percentage
Electrical measurements (e.g. current, voltage, charge, or any other electrical measurements)	32	45,07%
Plasma diagnostics (e.g. probe measurements, imaging, spectroscopy, or any other plasma diagnostic methods)	28	39,44%
Surface diagnostics (e.g. SEM, XPS, FTIR, or any other surface diagnostic methods)	20	28,17%
Modeling / Simulation methods (e.g. DFT, MD, PIC, CFD, fluid, or any other modeling / simulation methods)	28	39,44%
Other	1	1,41%
Not completed or Not displayed	10	14,08%

Comments (other):

- Biological application (mostly FACS analysis)

FAIR data principles

FAIR data are data which meet principles of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability^{4,5}. Did you already know these FAIR data principles?

Open Science

In favour of open science, more and more funding organisations, publishers, and institutional policies recommend or even require the publication of digital datasets in addition to traditional journal publications. Have you already published such datasets, e.g. as supplementary data or by means of third-party data repositories? Please name the service you may have used for data publications if applicable, and please also comment on the reasons why you have published datasets in the past, or why you did not do so.

Comments:

- LXCAT and ZDPLASKIN
- figshare; it was required by the journal.
- Because I do modeling, I reference datasets but do not produce them myself.
- Availability of community standard repository.
- INPTDAT, publishing with co-authors from INP.
- PURE
- I have not published anything yet.

⁴ M. D. Wilkinson et al., "The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship", Scientific Data 3 (2016) 160018.

⁵ FAIR Principles, <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

Have you already published such datasets, e.g. as supplementary data or by means of third-party data repositories?

In support of open science and the FAIR data principles, how open are you to sharing your pre-publication research output (datasets, research methods, etc.) with other researchers?

Answer	Count	Percentage
I am very open to sharing	16	22,54%
I am somewhat open to sharing	15	21,13%
I am hesitant to share (e.g. I might only share a portion of information with close colleagues or close to publication)	9	12,68%
I will not share until after my research has been formally published	3	4,23%
I am not sure	0	0,00%
No answer	0	0,00%
Not completed or Not displayed	28	39,44%

Factors

Which of the following factors influence your willingness to share your research outputs (apart from publications, i.e. datasets, research methods, etc.) with other researchers on a third party platform?

Previous Knowledge

Do you have experience in using knowledge graphs or related technologies (RDF, OWL, SPARQL) in your group? Please indicate which specific technologies you have experience with or have heard of.

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes, I have used	0	0,00%
Yes, I have heard of	1	1,41%
No	42	59,15%
Not completed or Not displayed	28	39,44%

Comments:

- Yes
- Was not really needed.
- Not familiar at all.
- I don't know very much about this theme.
- My research position is outdated (2014).
- I heard of OWL.

Are you generally aware of national or international projects focusing on management and sharing of scientific data, like the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), or the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI)?

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes, we are participating in the following project(s):	2	2,82%
Yes, I have heard of the following project(s):	12	16,90%
No	29	40,85%
Not completed or Not displayed	28	39,44%

Comments:

- ESCAPE (1x)
- LXCAT (2x)
- NFDI (4x)
- QPTDat (1x)
- EOSC (1x)
- Yes
- I don't know very much about this theme.
- My research position is outdated (2014).

Standards for electrical measurements

Do you carry out electric current measurements in your group? Please use the comment fields to indicate which specific standards or (meta-)data models are used.

Multiple answers possible (sum > 100%).

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes, and a published processing standard (e.g. ISO standard / DIN norm / DIN SPEC) is taken into account	3	4,23%
Yes, according to an internal processing standard	6	8,45%
Yes, and data files are stored according to a specific data model, e.g. prescribed file format and structure, device specific standards, proprietary file formats (Tektronix, Yokogawa, LeCroy, ...)	7	9,86%
Yes, and data files are uniformly documented (e.g. lab notes template, log files, or metadata schema to collect process parameters)	4	5,63%
Yes, it is the responsibility of individual staff members to ensure that the data can be found and used	11	15,49%
No	3	4,23%
Not completed or Not displayed	49	69,01%

Comments:

- DIN SPEC 91315
- No standards at that time
- Tektronix
- Standardized Origin Generated Graphics

Do you carry out voltage measurements in your group? Please use the comment fields to indicate which specific standards or (meta-)data models are used.

Multiple answers possible (sum > 100%).

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes, and a published processing standard (e.g. ISO standard / DIN norm / DIN SPEC) is taken into account	2	2,82%
Yes, according to an internal processing standard	4	5,63%
Yes, and data files are stored according to a specific data model, e.g. prescribed file format and structure, device specific standards, proprietary file formats (Tektronix, Yokogawa, LeCroy, ...)	7	9,86%
Yes, and data files are uniformly documented (e.g. lab notes template, log files, or metadata schema to collect process parameters)	4	5,63%
Yes, it is the responsibility of individual staff members to ensure that the data can be found and used	12	16,90%
No	2	2,82%
Not completed or Not displayed	49	69,01%

Do you carry out electric charge measurements in your group? Please use the comment fields to indicate which specific standards or (meta-)data models are used.

Multiple answers possible (sum > 100%).

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes, and a published processing standard (e.g. ISO standard / DIN norm / DIN SPEC) is taken into account	0	0,00%
Yes, according to an internal processing standard	2	2,82%
Yes, and data files are stored according to a specific data model, e.g. prescribed file format and structure, device specific standards, proprietary file formats (Tektronix, Yokogawa, LeCroy, ...)	3	4,23%
Yes, and data files are uniformly documented (e.g. lab notes template, log files, or metadata schema to collect process parameters)	3	4,23%
Yes, it is the responsibility of individual staff members to ensure that the data can be found and used	7	9,86%
No	10	14,08%
Not completed or Not displayed	49	69,01%

Attendance in subsection: 30.99%

In your opinion, are there other electrical measurement methods that urgently require recognized standards for quality assurance? If yes, please name relevant methods and comment on your opinion:

- The first problem is to separate measurements and artifacts. I am not worried about 95% of data, which have been “measured”. The data are documented with a pen in a Lab-book. I have not understood the questions.
- I feel that guides and schemes are needed to standardize and improve the quality of high-frequency and pulsed I-V measurements.

- Safety qualification/classification for research purpose, especially when everybody is talking plasma medicine but not even judging harmful current or so.
- E-field measurements, Electromagnetic noise or parasite signals.

Are you generally of the opinion that a standardized execution of electrical measurements and/or uniform storage and documentation according to suitable data models and metadata standards could help to ensure the quality and re-usability of data obtained from such measurements? Please comment on your opinion.

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes	11	15,49%
Not sure	9	12,68%
No	2	2,82%
No answer	0	0,00%
Not completed or Not displayed	49	69,01%

Comments:

- The problem is a possible limitation of novel approaches by such standards.
- I have not understood the questions.
- But be aware of freedom in the interpretation of standards.
- I think that “standardized execution of electrical measurements” is important, but “uniform storage and documentation according to suitable data models and metadata standards” is not possible or important and is in most cases a waste of time.
- I somehow hesitate to define new standards, that have to be met and put into place without having additional time. Projects are becoming more and more urgent and pressed for time. So the daily lab routine is shortened everywhere. Some institutes also require data storage on paper, digital, AND repertories, hence the user has to go through several loops to finish storing. All that burns time, that should be dedicated to research instead of bureaucratic standards, that are not put together. Hence, this approach should consider REPLACING instead of enhancing these old-fashioned standards.
- In the field of welding: I think documentation is the most important part of most applications since standardized measurement setups would require significant changes to many labs.
- It is of great importance to know as much as possible about the experimental conditions, the characterization method, and the acquisition of the data, as for later reproducibility / standardization / proving the quality of the taken data.

Plasma Diagnostics

Do you carry out Langmuir probe measurements in your group? Please use the comment fields to indicate which specific standards or (meta-)data models are used.

Multiple answers possible (sum > 100%).

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes, and a published processing standard (e.g. ISO standard / DIN norm / DIN SPEC) is taken into account	0	0,00%
Yes, according to an internal processing standard	4	5,63%
Yes, and data files are stored according to a specific data model, e.g. prescribed file format and structure, device specific standards, proprietary file formats	1	1,41%
Yes, and data files are uniformly documented (e.g. lab notes template, log files, or metadata schema to collect process parameters)	4	5,63%
Yes, it is the responsibility of individual staff members to ensure that the data can be found and used	4	5,63%
No	11	15,49%
Not completed or Not displayed	52	73,24%

Do you carry out ICCD or streak camera imaging in your group? Please use the comment fields to indicate which specific standards or (meta-)data models are used.

Multiple answers possible (sum > 100%).

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes, and a published processing standard (e.g. ISO standard / DIN norm / DIN SPEC) is taken into account	0	0,00%
Yes, according to an internal processing standard	6	8,45%
Yes, and data files are stored according to a specific data model, e.g. prescribed file format and structure, device specific standards, proprietary file formats	3	4,23%
Yes, and data files are uniformly documented (e.g. lab notes template, log files, or metadata schema to collect process parameters)	4	5,63%
Yes, it is the responsibility of individual staff members to ensure that the data can be found and used	10	14,08%
No	5	7,04%
Not completed or Not displayed	52	73,24%

Do you apply optical emission spectroscopy (OES) in your group? Please use the comment fields to indicate which specific standards or (meta-)data models are used.

Multiple answers possible (sum > 100%).

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes, and a published processing standard (e.g. ISO standard / DIN norm / DIN SPEC) is taken into account	2	2,82%
Yes, according to an internal processing standard	6	8,45%
Yes, and data files are stored according to a specific data model, e.g. prescribed file format and structure, device specific standards, proprietary file formats	4	5,63%
Yes, and data files are uniformly documented (e.g. lab notes template, log files, or metadata schema to collect process parameters)	5	7,04%
Yes, it is the responsibility of individual staff members to ensure that the data can be found and used	11	15,49%
No	1	1,41%
Not completed or Not displayed	52	73,24%

Comments:

- DIN SPEC 91315
- ISO
- Mostly according to Avaspec output file.

Do you apply absorption spectroscopy in your group? Please use the comment fields to indicate which specific standards or (meta-)data models are used.

Multiple answers possible (sum > 100%).

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes, and a published processing standard (e.g. ISO standard / DIN norm / DIN SPEC) is taken into account	1	1,41%
Yes, according to an internal processing standard	4	5,63%
Yes, and data files are stored according to a specific data model, e.g. prescribed file format and structure, device specific standards, proprietary file formats	2	2,82%
Yes, and data files are uniformly documented (e.g. lab notes template, log files, or metadata schema to collect process parameters)	3	4,23%
Yes, it is the responsibility of individual staff members to ensure that the data can be found and used	7	9,86%
No	7	9,86%
Not completed or Not displayed	52	73,24%

Comments:

- ISO

Do you apply laser-induced fluorescence (LIF) in your group? Please use the comment fields to indicate which specific standards or (meta-)data models are used.

Multiple answers possible (sum > 100%).

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes, and a published processing standard (e.g. ISO standard / DIN norm / DIN SPEC) is taken into account	0	0,00%
Yes, according to an internal processing standard	3	4,23%
Yes, and data files are stored according to a specific data model, e.g. prescribed file format and structure, device specific standards, proprietary file formats	1	1,41%
Yes, and data files are uniformly documented (e.g. lab notes template, log files, or metadata schema to collect process parameters)	1	1,41%
Yes, it is the responsibility of individual staff members to ensure that the data can be found and used	5	7,04%
No	11	15,49%
Not completed or Not displayed	52	73,24%

Do you apply microwave interferometry in your group? Please use the comment fields to indicate which specific standards or (meta-)data models are used.

Multiple answers possible (sum > 100%).

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes, and a published processing standard (e.g. ISO standard / DIN norm / DIN SPEC) is taken into account	0	0,00%
Yes, according to an internal processing standard	2	2,82%
Yes, and data files are stored according to a specific data model, e.g. prescribed file format and structure, device specific standards, proprietary file formats	0	0,00%
Yes, and data files are uniformly documented (e.g. lab notes template, log files, or metadata schema to collect process parameters)	0	0,00%
Yes, it is the responsibility of individual staff members to ensure that the data can be found and used	1	1,41%
No	16	22,54%
Not completed or Not displayed	52	73,24%

Do you carry out mass spectrometry (MS) in your group? Please use the comment fields to indicate which specific standards or (meta-)data models are used.

Multiple answers possible (sum > 100%).

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes, and a published processing standard (e.g. ISO standard / DIN norm / DIN SPEC) is taken into account	1	1,41%
Yes, according to an internal processing standard	0	0,00%
Yes, and data files are stored according to a specific data model, e.g. prescribed file format and structure, device specific standards, proprietary file formats	0	0,00%
Yes, and data files are uniformly documented (e.g. lab notes template, log files, or metadata schema to collect process parameters)	2	2,82%
Yes, it is the responsibility of individual staff members to ensure that the data can be found and used	4	5,63%
No	11	15,49%
Not completed or Not displayed	52	73,24%

Comments:

- ISO
- Not in my group, but in collaboration with another group.

Do you apply Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) in your group? Please use the comment fields to indicate which specific standards or (meta-)data models are used.

Multiple answers possible (sum > 100%).

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes, and a published processing standard (e.g. ISO standard / DIN norm / DIN SPEC) is taken into account	1	1,41%
Yes, according to an internal processing standard	1	1,41%
Yes, and data files are stored according to a specific data model, e.g. prescribed file format and structure, device specific standards, proprietary file formats	2	2,82%
Yes, and data files are uniformly documented (e.g. lab notes template, log files, or metadata schema to collect process parameters)	2	2,82%
Yes, it is the responsibility of individual staff members to ensure that the data can be found and used	6	8,45%
No	8	11,27%
Not completed or Not displayed	52	73,24%

Comments:

- ISO
- Not in my group, but in collaboration with another group.

Attendance in subsection: 26.76%

In your opinion, are there other plasma diagnostic methods that urgently require recognized standards for quality assurance? If yes, please name relevant methods and comment on your opinion:

- All methods require some standards but it is difficult within the community to agree on those and quality can vary quite a lot, particularly in the interpretation of the data, not so much on the data acquisition itself.
- No
- E-field measurements, VUV measurements, Schlieren photography.

Are you generally of the opinion that a standardized execution of plasma diagnostics and/or uniform storage and documentation according to suitable data models and metadata standards could help to ensure the quality and re-usability of data obtained from such measurements? Please comment on your opinion.

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes	8	11,27%
Not sure	8	11,27%
No	3	4,23%
No answer	0	0,00%
Not completed or Not displayed	52	73,24%

Comments:

- This data is more complex than electrical measurement data and therefore a standard would help.
- I have not understood the questions.
- See previous page.
- No, because many setups are quite unique and particularly because the main issues are in the data interpretation and not in the data acquisition itself. There are nevertheless issues in the data acquisition itself that could be resolved by defining “good practices”. Defining “standards” may be too cumbersome and of little help.

Surface Diagnostics

Do you apply scanning electron microscopy (SEM) in your group? Please use the comment fields to indicate which specific standards or (meta-)data models are used.

Multiple answers possible (sum > 100%).

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes, and a published processing standard (e.g. ISO standard / DIN norm / DIN SPEC) is taken into account	1	1,41%
Yes, according to an internal processing standard	1	1,41%
Yes, and data files are stored according to a specific data model, e.g. prescribed file format and structure, device specific standards, proprietary file formats	1	1,41%
Yes, and data files are uniformly documented (e.g. lab notes template, log files, or metadata schema to collect process parameters)	2	2,82%
Yes, it is the responsibility of individual staff members to ensure that the data can be found and used	4	5,63%
No	3	4,23%
Not completed or Not displayed	59	83,10%

Comments:

- ISO
- Not in my group, but in collaboration with another group.

Do you apply X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) in your group? Please use the comment fields to indicate which specific standards or (meta-)data models are used.

Multiple answers possible (sum > 100%).

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes, and a published processing standard (e.g. ISO standard / DIN norm / DIN SPEC) is taken into account	1	1,41%
Yes, according to an internal processing standard	0	0,00%
Yes, and data files are stored according to a specific data model, e.g. prescribed file format and structure, device specific standards, proprietary file formats	0	0,00%
Yes, and data files are uniformly documented (e.g. lab notes template, log files, or metadata schema to collect process parameters)	3	4,23%
Yes, it is the responsibility of individual staff members to ensure that the data can be found and used	5	7,04%
No	2	2,82%
Not completed or Not displayed	59	83,10%

Comments:

- ISO
- Not in my group, but in collaboration with another group.

Do you apply energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS / ESX) in your group? Please use the comment fields to indicate which specific standards or (meta-)data models are used.

Multiple answers possible (sum > 100%).

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes, and a published processing standard (e.g. ISO standard / DIN norm / DIN SPEC) is taken into account	1	1,41%
Yes, according to an internal processing standard	0	0,00%
Yes, and data files are stored according to a specific data model, e.g. prescribed file format and structure, device specific standards, proprietary file formats	1	1,41%
Yes, and data files are uniformly documented (e.g. lab notes template, log files, or metadata schema to collect process parameters)	2	2,82%
Yes, it is the responsibility of individual staff members to ensure that the data can be found and used	2	2,82%
No	5	7,04%
Not completed or Not displayed	59	83,10%

Comments:

- ISO

Do you apply Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) in your group? Please use the comment fields to indicate which specific standards or (meta-)data models are used.

Multiple answers possible (sum > 100%).

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes, and a published processing standard (e.g. ISO standard / DIN norm / DIN SPEC) is taken into account	1	1,41%
Yes, according to an internal processing standard	0	0,00%
Yes, and data files are stored according to a specific data model, e.g. prescribed file format and structure, device specific standards, proprietary file formats	2	2,82%
Yes, and data files are uniformly documented (e.g. lab notes template, log files, or metadata schema to collect process parameters)	2	2,82%
Yes, it is the responsibility of individual staff members to ensure that the data can be found and used	4	5,63%
No	4	5,63%
Not completed or Not displayed	59	83,10%

Comments:

- ISO
- Not in my group, but in collaboration with another group.

Do you apply atomic force microscopy (AFM) in your group? Please use the comment fields to indicate which specific standards or (meta-)data models are used.

Multiple answers possible (sum > 100%).

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes, and a published processing standard (e.g. ISO standard / DIN norm / DIN SPEC) is taken into account	1	1,41%
Yes, according to an internal processing standard	0	0,00%
Yes, and data files are stored according to a specific data model, e.g. prescribed file format and structure, device specific standards, proprietary file formats	0	0,00%
Yes, and data files are uniformly documented (e.g. lab notes template, log files, or metadata schema to collect process parameters)	1	1,41%
Yes, it is the responsibility of individual staff members to ensure that the data can be found and used	3	4,23%
No	6	8,45%
Not completed or Not displayed	59	83,10%

Comments:

- ISO
- Not in my group, but in collaboration with another group.

Do you apply contact angle measurements in your group? Please use the comment fields to indicate which specific standards or (meta-)data models are used.

Multiple answers possible (sum > 100%).

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes, and a published processing standard (e.g. ISO standard / DIN norm / DIN SPEC) is taken into account	1	1,41%
Yes, according to an internal processing standard	2	2,82%
Yes, and data files are stored according to a specific data model, e.g. prescribed file format and structure, device specific standards, proprietary file formats	1	1,41%
Yes, and data files are uniformly documented (e.g. lab notes template, log files, or metadata schema to collect process parameters)	3	4,23%
Yes, it is the responsibility of individual staff members to ensure that the data can be found and used	6	8,45%
No	2	2,82%
Not completed or Not displayed	59	83,10%

Comments:

- ISO

Do you apply thermography / thermal imaging in your group? Please use the comment fields to indicate which specific standards or (meta-)data models are used.

Multiple answers possible (sum > 100%).

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes, and a published processing standard (e.g. ISO standard / DIN norm / DIN SPEC) is taken into account	0	0,00%
Yes, according to an internal processing standard	0	0,00%
Yes, and data files are stored according to a specific data model, e.g. prescribed file format and structure, device specific standards, proprietary file formats	1	1,41%
Yes, and data files are uniformly documented (e.g. lab notes template, log files, or metadata schema to collect process parameters)	0	0,00%
Yes, it is the responsibility of individual staff members to ensure that the data can be found and used	0	0,00%
No	10	14,08%
Not completed or Not displayed	59	83,10%

Comments:

- Not in my group, but in collaboration with another group.

Attendance in subsection: 16.90%

In your opinion, are there other surface diagnostic methods that urgently require recognized standards for quality assurance? If yes, please name relevant methods and comment on your opinion:

- Raman, TEM, RBS,

Are you generally of the opinion that a standardized execution of surface diagnostics and/or uniform storage and documentation according to suitable data models and metadata standards could help to ensure the quality and re-usability of data obtained from such measurements? Please comment on your opinion.

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes	7	9,86%
Not sure	5	7,04%
No	0	0,00%
No answer	0	0,00%
Not completed or Not displayed	59	83,10%

Comments:

- See previous comment.
- Surface diagnostics techniques are a quite mature field and some kind of standardization may help improve the quality of measurements done in relation to plasma research.

Standards for modelling / simulation methods

Do you carry out kinetic Boltzmann calculations in your group? Please use the comment fields to indicate which specific standards or (meta-)data models are used.

Multiple answers possible (sum > 100%).

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes, and data files are stored according to a specific data model (e.g. prescribed file format and structure)	4	5,63%
Yes, and data files are uniformly documented (e.g. lab notes template, log files, or metadata schema to collect simulation parameters)	1	1,41%
Yes, it is the responsibility of individual staff members to ensure that the data can be found and used	10	14,08%
No	6	8,45%
Not completed or Not displayed	51	71,83%

Comments:

- We often use Bolsig+/- but also have an in-house swarm code with its own format.
- We have homemade cross-section files but also use the LXCat cross-section files, which happen to have a format; but we don't adhere to it.
- Date, key parameters, publication

Do you carry out density functional theory simulations (DFT) in your group? Please use the comment fields to indicate which specific standards or (meta-)data models are used.

Multiple answers possible (sum > 100%).

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes, and data files are stored according to a specific data model (e.g. prescribed file format and structure)	2	2,82%
Yes, and data files are uniformly documented (e.g. lab notes template, log files, or metadata schema to collect simulation parameters)	1	1,41%
Yes, it is the responsibility of individual staff members to ensure that the data can be found and used	3	4,23%
No	16	22,54%
Not completed or Not displayed	51	71,83%

Do you carry out molecular dynamics simulations (MD) in your group? Please use the comment fields to indicate which specific standards or (meta-)data models are used.

Multiple answers possible (sum > 100%).

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes, and data files are stored according to a specific data model (e.g. prescribed file format and structure)	1	1,41%
Yes, and data files are uniformly documented (e.g. lab notes template, log files, or metadata schema to collect simulation parameters)	2	2,82%

Yes, it is the responsibility of individual staff members to ensure that the data can be found and used	5	7,04%
No	15	21,13%
Not completed or Not displayed	51	71,83%

Comments:

- Date, key parameters, publication

Do you carry out kinetic Monte Carlo simulations (KMC) in your group? Please use the comment fields to indicate which specific standards or (meta-)data models are used.

Multiple answers possible (sum > 100%).

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes, and data files are stored according to a specific data model (e.g. prescribed file format and structure)	1	1,41%
Yes, and data files are uniformly documented (e.g. lab notes template, log files, or metadata schema to collect simulation parameters)	2	2,82%
Yes, it is the responsibility of individual staff members to ensure that the data can be found and used	7	9,86%
No	11	15,49%
Not completed or Not displayed	51	71,83%

Comments:

- Date, key parameters, publication

Do you carry out particle-in-cell simulations (PIC) in your group? Please use the comment fields to indicate which specific standards or (meta-)data models are used.

Multiple answers possible (sum > 100%).

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes, and data files are stored according to a specific data model (e.g. prescribed file format and structure)	4	5,63%
Yes, and data files are uniformly documented (e.g. lab notes template, log files, or metadata schema to collect simulation parameters)	3	4,23%
Yes, it is the responsibility of individual staff members to ensure that the data can be found and used	8	11,27%
No	6	8,45%
Not completed or Not displayed	51	71,83%

Comments:

- We use Silo files for output, custom config files for input, and LXCAT style cross sections.
- We have homemade cross-section files but also use the LXCat cross-section files, which happen to have a format; but we don't adhere to it.
- Date, key parameters, publication

Do you carry out hydrodynamic plasma simulations in your group? Please use the comment fields to indicate which specific standards or (meta-)data models are used.

Multiple answers possible (sum > 100%).

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes, and data files are stored according to a specific data model (e.g. prescribed file format and structure)	4	5,63%
Yes, and data files are uniformly documented (e.g. lab notes template, log files, or metadata schema to collect simulation parameters)	2	2,82%
Yes, it is the responsibility of individual staff members to ensure that the data can be found and used	10	14,08%
No	6	8,45%
Not completed or Not displayed	51	71,83%

Comments:

- We use Silo files for output, custom config files for input, and custom input files for electron transport/reactions and chemistry.
- This is a smaller research area for us so all data files are constructed ourselves from published data.
- Date, key parameters, publication

Do you carry out magnetohydrodynamics simulations (MHD) in your group? Please use the comment fields to indicate which specific standards or (meta-)data models are used.

Multiple answers possible (sum > 100%).

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes, and data files are stored according to a specific data model (e.g. prescribed file format and structure)	1	1,41%
Yes, and data files are uniformly documented (e.g. lab notes template, log files, or metadata schema to collect simulation parameters)	0	0,00%
Yes, it is the responsibility of individual staff members to ensure that the data can be found and used	6	8,45%
No	13	18,31%
Not completed or Not displayed	51	71,83%

Do you carry out computational fluid dynamics simulations (CFD) in your group? Please use the comment fields to indicate which specific standards or (meta-)data models are used.

Multiple answers possible (sum > 100%).

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes, and data files are stored according to a specific data model (e.g. prescribed file format and structure)	3	4,23%
Yes, and data files are uniformly documented (e.g. lab notes template, log files, or metadata schema to collect simulation parameters)	1	1,41%

Yes, it is the responsibility of individual staff members to ensure that the data can be found and used	11	15,49%
No	7	9,86%
Not completed or Not displayed	51	71,83%

Comments:

- This is a smaller research area for us so all data files are constructed ourselves from published data.
- Date, key parameters, publication

Attendance in subsection: 28.17%

In your opinion, are there other modeling / simulation methods that urgently require recognized standards for quality assurance? If yes, please name relevant methods and comment on your opinion:

- 0D global models for chemistry
- - cross sections (in particular elastic/momentum/effective etc on LXCAT)
 - Chemical reaction data sets for different applications (e.g. dry air up to $t = \dots$)
 - Reaction coefficients on plasma-liquid interfaces (like air - water)

Are you generally of the opinion that a standardized storage and documentation of modeling and simulation procedures in accordance with suitable data models and metadata standards could help to ensure the quality and re-usability of data obtained from such methods? Please comment on your opinion.

Answer	Count	Percentage
Yes	12	16,90%
Not sure	7	9,86%
No	1	1,41%
No answer	0	0,00%
Not completed or Not displayed	51	71,83%

Comments:

- See previous comment.
- Surface diagnostics techniques are a quite mature field and some kind of standardization may help improve the quality of measurements done in relation to plasma research.

Are you generally of the opinion that a standardized storage and documentation of modeling and simulation procedures in accordance with suitable data models and metadata standards could help to ensure the quality and re-usability of data obtained from suc

